

Accumulation of Serum Amyloid A fibrils in mouse brain following chronic Systemic Amyloidosis

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ABSTRACT

Prolonged injection of casein results in Systemic amyloidosis in mice with impaired hepatic functions due to excessive serum amyloid A (SAA) fibril deposition in liver, spleen and kidney. In the present work, we have shown that Systemic amyloidosis results in accumulation of SAA fibrils in the brain. We have carried out radiolabeling studies to source the SAA fibrils and serum amyloid P component (SAP) that are present in the brain of the affected mice. Results of these experiments suggest that the systemic amyloidosis results in selective crossing of SAA and SAP proteins through blood brain barrier (BBB). Injection of ¹²⁵I SAA and ¹²⁵I SAP to casein treated mice resulted in the accumulation of these proteins in the liver to the maximum extent and to about 20% (compared to liver) localization in the brain. The Congo red stained polarizing microscopic pictures of the cerebral cortex have shown the presence of amyloid fibrils in the brain of the mice with systemic amyloidosis. Immunohistochemical studies also indicate that the abundance of SAA and SAP in the mice brain following chronic systemic amyloidosis condition. The present study provides a basis for investigation on the effect of systemic amyloidosis to the brain in chronic inflammation of mouse.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Serum Amyloid A (SAA) is an acute phase reactant, whose level in the blood is elevated to 1000 fold when the body is subjected to various metabolic insults like trauma, infection, inflammation, and neoplasia [1]. Increased SAA, with decreased apolipoprotein and reduction of cholesterol level in the high-density lipoprotein (HDL) are the pathological markers of the inflammatory condition. The enhanced level of the SAA usually results in reactive amyloid deposits, which is mainly composed SAA fibril. SAA is a polymorphic protein; at least 7 genomic clones and corresponding different types of proteins have been identified [2,3]. Among them SAA1 and SAA2 are the acute phase reactant (collectively called A-SAA) [4,5]. SAA fibrils are known to get deposited in many vital organs and causing symptoms such as

spleen and renal insufficiency. Further, in the peripheral organs increased SAA result in high affinity to macrophages and more importantly reduces the anti-oxidizing effects of high-density lipoprotein on low-density lipoprotein (LDL). Apart from this, SAA protein in the peripheral organs is also known to play a very active role in events leading to inflammation [6]. Prolonged hyper-production of SAA leads to amyloid fibril formation in peripheral organs. This condition is characterized by insoluble SAA fibrils in the liver, spleen, and kidney of the affected individuals. The amyloid A (SAA) fibrils are composed of 8.5kDa monomers. The liver is the primary source of the plasma SAA, even though the extra hepatic production of SAA has also been reported [7-13]. Hepatocytes increase the synthesis of SAA by inflammatory cytokine stimuli, such as tumor necrosis factor (TNF), interleukin-1 (IL) and IL-6 [14-16]. Thus SAA is

expressed in abundance in many pathological lesions [17]. Like SAA and serum amyloid P component (SAP) is another acute phase reactant, found to be up-regulated in amyloidotic condition. It is a glycoprotein composed of subunit of approximately 25 kDa that has been found in association with almost all types of amyloid deposits. It is suggested that by controlling SAP production at the tissue level, the inflammatory damage in the brain due to Alzheimer's disease (AD) may be controlled. The present work aims explore the possibility of SAA and SAP crossing the BBB and getting accumulated in the brain in systemic amyloidotic condition. For the first time we have shown that in chronic amyloidotic conditions, SAA and SAP are selectively transported to the brain, which resulted in SAA and SAP accumulation in the brain.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Production of Systemic Amyloidosis

Colony-bred adult male Swiss White mice (30-35 g) were used. Animals were selected randomly and caged in groups of four at room temperature (25-35° C) and supplied with food (Commercial pelleted animal feed marketed by M/s. Hindustan Lever, Bombay, India under the name "Gold Mohur rat feed") and tap water ad libitum (control n=5, test n=5). All animal procedures were carried out as approved by the Animal Care and Use Committee of Central Leather Research Institute, Chennai. Mice were given 0.5 ml of 10% Vitamin free Casein (1CN Pharmaceuticals, Cleveland, OH, USA) as subcutaneous injection [18] for 66 days to induce systemic amyloidosis. Control animals were treated with saline. At the end of treatment, animals were decapitated. Immediately after decapitation, brain cerebral cortex, liver, and spleen were removed in the ice-chilled condition for further analysis. Systemic amyloidosis was confirmed by "ladder formation" in the liver. The presence of amyloid fibrils in the liver and Spleen is further confirmed by Congo red staining.

2.2. Congo red staining of brain, liver, and Spleen amyloid deposits

Frozen tissue sections were analyzed for amyloid deposition with Congo red staining by following the reported procedure [19]. In brief, the deparaffinized sections were stained with Mayer's solution for 1 min and then rinsed in saline solution for few minutes. Sections are treated in solution containing 10gm NaCl to 100ml in 80% (v/v) ethanol for 20 min. These sections are transferred directly over to solution in 2gm Congo red and 10 gm NaCl to 1000ml 80% ethanol stained for 20 min. The sections were then washed twice with absolute ethanol. The sections were then washed with xylene thrice and mounted under cover glass in a synthetic mounting medium, DPX. Stained sections were observed with light and crossed

high intensity polarizes in polarization microscopy (EUROMAX, Holland).

2.3 Immunostaining of brain endothelial cell capillaries

Brain capillary endothelial cells were prepared as described previously [20]. Briefly, six fresh Swiss White mice brains were homogenized with 0.4M sucrose containing, 0.1 mM CaCl₂, 1mM ATP, and 0.5mM MES buffer pH 6.1. The homogenate were filtered using 50-60 size nylon meshes. The filtrate was centrifuged at 7000g for 45 min. The resulting supernatant was passed through the 1.1 × 40 cm Sephadex G-25 columns. Final purification was achieved by foam fractionation in a media of high surface-active substance, such as bovine serum albumin. The endothelial cells were identified by their characteristic morphology of extremely attenuated flattened shapes with nuclei lining the capillaries. The capillaries are viewed with in the inverted phase-contrast microscopy (Olympus CK30-F200, Japan). After fixing the portion of the brain endothelial cells over the glass slides, the immuno labeling were carried out by following procedure. Rabbit polyclonal antibody to mice SAA, which recognize the SAA fibrils and monomer, was used for immunolabeling. The whole serum was diluted 1:1000 in 0.1M phosphate buffer saline, pH 7.4. After blocking the nonspecific binding with 2% BSA solutions, the section were incubated for 30 min the room temperature in SAA primary antibody. Controls were incubated with non-immune rabbit serum (diluted with 1:1000) and with anti SAA antibody. After washing the sections were treated with FITC conjugated secondary antibody (Sigma, USA). Fluorescence in the slides was observed Zeiss fluorescence microscopy (AXIO plan2, Carl ZEISS NAG f. HBO50, Germany). Similarly, the brain endothelial cell capillaries were also treated with anti rabbit SAP, and its binding was observed as above by fluorescence microscopy.

2.4. Isolation of SAA

SAA was isolated from the plasma of casein injected [18] mice as reported previously by Lindhorst et al [21]. It was then characterized using 17% SDS-polyacrylamide gels. Isolated SAA was purified by Waters reverse phase-high performance liquid chromatography [22] (RP-HPLC) analytical column 4.6 × 250 mm Spherisorb ODS2 LC₁₈ (Waters, Milford, Massachusetts, USA) and size exclusion chromatography (SEC) columns using a series of 7.8 × 300 mm Ultrahydrogel 250™ and Ultrahydrogel 500™ the molecular weight was determined (Waters, Milford, Massachusetts, USA).

2.5. Isolation of SAP

SAP was isolated from plasma of casein-injected mice. The pooled plasma was processed for SAP extraction as previously described [23]. 12% SDS-Polyacrylamide gels

characterized SAP. The isolated SAP was purified by Waters RP-HPLC analytical column 4.6 × 250 mm Spherisorb ODS2 LC₁₈ (Waters, Milford, Massachusetts, USA) and the molecular weight determined by SEC columns used to 7.8 × 300 mm Ultrahydrogel 250™, Ultrahydrogel 500™ (Waters, Kyoto, Japan.) column series [21].

2.6. Immunostaining of brain sections

The antisera against SAA and SAP were prepared as per the following procedure. Briefly, New Zealand White rabbits were given intradermal injection of 0.1 mg/ml of mouse SAA was given weekly once; prior to the injection, the SAA protein was dissolved in PBS and emulsified in complete and incomplete adjuvant. Three weeks later a fourth intradermal injection was given and the animal were bled in the following week. The antisera were stored for further processing in -20°C. By following similar procedure antisera produced against SAP also the immunostaining of SAA and SAP in the brain is carried out as follows; after blocking the nonspecific binding with 2% BSA solutions, after brain tissue sections were incubated with anti SAA for 30 min. at 4°C. After washing in PBS, the sections were incubated with FITC conjugated rabbit anti mouse antibody for 30 min. at 4°C. Similarly the antisera set of brain section was prepared against SAP for 30 min. at 4°C. After washing in PBS and then incubated with FITC conjugated rabbit anti mouse antibody for 30 min. at 4°C, the FITC fluorescence was observed by fluorescence microscopy.

2.7. Radio labeling

The SAA and SAP was labelled with ¹²⁵I (Baba Atomic Research Center, New Mumbai, India) using the method by Hamazaki [24] and stored in phosphate buffered saline containing 0.02% NaN₃. Labelled proteins to a final specific activity of approximately 2mCi/mM were given to amyloidotic and control mice. ¹²⁵I BSA used as a control. After 24 hrs, animals were sacrificed and the organs (brain, liver, and spleen) and plasma were measured in a 1270 Rack Gamma II γ counter (Pharmacia Biotech (LKB), Uppsala, Sweden). All the groups compared statistically using the Chi-square test, U-Test (Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon) and analysis of variance (ANOVA) with 2-tailed significance thresholds.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Congo red staining fibrils in the brain, liver, and Spleen

The effect of systemic amyloidosis in liver and spleen were examined by analyzing the deposits by Congo red staining. We have also examined the brain sections of mice affected in systemic amyloidosis by this procedure. The Congo red staining of the liver, spleen, and

cerebral cortex reveals that the large amount of fibrils in liver and spleen as reported earlier [25] diffused amyloid deposits dispersed throughout the cerebral cortex, with occasional accumulation in few places. However, neither diffuse nor localized amyloid deposits were present in the control mice. This more evident when the sections are viewed under the cross polarized filters (Fig. 1b, d, and f). A golden yellow birefringence amyloid deposit is seen in the middle with diffused smaller sized deposit distributed around the brain tissue section (Fig. 1b) in the case of mice with systemic amyloidosis. Similar deposits are also seen in the case of liver and spleen (Fig. 1d and f). However in the control mice, small dot-like structures were visible in the mice brain, the origin of which is unclear (Fig. 1a). In the case of control liver these dot like structure are more prevalent (Fig. 1c). In spleen we could see more diffused amyloid deposits even in control mice (Fig. 1e).

3.2. Transport of SAA and SAP across the blood brain barrier

Suki et al [26] have previously reported an enhanced accumulation of SAA protein in the brain of hypertensive monkey. Sourcing of this type of amyloid accumulation can be either due to local production or uptake from the blood. Considering the abundance of SAA expression in the peripheral tissues and enhanced the levels of SAA in the blood, the transport of SAA to brain tissues through the blood brain barrier is not totally ruled out. To find out whether SAA could pass the BBB, we injected the radio labeled ¹²⁵I SAA and ¹²⁵I SAP in the control and casein injected mice (mice with systemic amyloidosis). Fig. 2a indicates that the radiolabeled SAA enters into the brain of the mice affected by systemic amyloidosis. The SAA incorporation to the brain tissue is specific to the SAA in the amyloidotic condition, because the amyloidotic mice when injected with radio labeled ¹²⁵I BSA shows negligible accumulation of ¹²⁵I BSA in the brain. This observation precludes the possibility of leaky brain endothelial cell capillaries, which will allow most of the proteins to be diffused in the inflammatory conditions.

Further, radio labeled ¹²⁵I SAA and ¹²⁵I BSA to the control shows no significant incorporation in the brain (Fig. 2a). The radio labeling analysis of the SAA is also carried out in plasma, liver, and spleen. Most of the SAA injected got accumulated in liver both control and amyloidotic mice (Fig. 2b). However in the spleen there is decreased accumulation when compared to that of liver (Fig. 2c). It should be mentioned that in control mice also got the SAA protein accumulated in the liver and spleen to the same extend. This may be due to general ability of SAA retention in these tissues, which explain their propensity to get accumulated amyloid deposits. It should be noted that for the control spleen show more diffused congophilic

Fig.1. Congo red stained sections as viewed under the cross-polarized filters. (a) brain cerebral cortex of control mice (c) liver of control mice (e) spleen of control mice. (b) golden yellow birefringence amyloid deposit is seen in the cerebral cortex of mice with systemic amyloidosis (d) amyloid fibrils also seen in liver (f) and spleen of the mice affected by systemic amyloidosis.

regions (Fig. 1c and e). The SAA level in the plasma was also higher than in the spleen, suggesting the clearance of SAA excretion is low (Fig. 2d). However the total clearance in the ^{125}I BSA in plasma, liver and spleen indicate the protein is totally excreted within 24hrs from time of the injection. Even though the amount of SAA incorporation to the brain is not very high as in the case of plasma, liver, and spleen, there is still a significant accumulation found in the brain in the amyloidotic mice when compared to the control. The other amyloid associated protein; namely SAP also get accumulated in liver and

spleen most importantly in brain (Fig. 3a, b, c, and d). A slightly higher accumulation of SAP in all the organs when compared with SAA is to be noted.

3.3. SAA and SAP binding to the brain endothelial cell capillaries

Either the transport or accumulation of SAA and SAP to the brain has to be through the endothelial cell binding/expression. The Immunostaining of brain endothelial cell capillaries shows the presence of SAA and SAP

Blood brain penetration of SAA

Fig. 2. Incorporation of ^{125}I Labelled SAA and ^{125}I Labelled BSA in the control and Casein injected mice. (a) Accumulation of ^{125}I SAA in Casein injected brain. Note less significant accumulation in the control mice. (b), (c) and (d). Shows correspondingly, liver, spleen, and plasma level ^{125}I SAA in both control and Casein injected mice. Data show mean γ counting values (\pm SEM) from single, representative experiments. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$, related to control conditions.

in the endothelial cells of mice with systemic amyloidosis with antibody raised against SAA and SAP. The fluorescence microscopic picture shows that SAA selectively binds to the brain endothelial cell capillaries (Fig. 4a). In Fig. 4b control and endothelial capillaries show no staining. Further in the case of SAP, the brain endothelial cell capillaries were also stained. As seen in the picture shows that SAA selectively binds to the brain endothelial cell capillaries (Fig. 4c). In the control endothelial cell capillaries shows no staining on treated antibody against SAP. The level of SAP binding/expression in the mice brain endothelial cell capillaries was much greater than the degree of SAA binding/expression.

3.4. Immunostaining for SAA and SAP in the mice brain

The SAA and SAP accumulation of the brain tissues were further confirmed by immunostaining the brain tissues with antibodies stained against these proteins. Fig. 5b indicates the presence of SAA in the brain tissues. In Fig. 5d presence of SAP is indicated by the fluorescence microscopy. However in the control mice we got the minimal fluorescence in for both SAA and SAP protein (Fig. 5a and c).

The inflammatory response in pathologically affected regions of amyloid deposition in the brain particularly in AD is well established [27]. As in the case of peripheral degenerating tissues, damaged neurons and neurite provide stimuli for inflammation. This will lead to up regulation of acute phase reactants and cytokines [28]. Thus, the SAA and SAP level

Blood brain penetration of SAP

Fig.3. Incorporation of ^{125}I labelled SAP and ^{125}I Labelled BSA in the control and Casein injected mice. (a) Accumulation of ^{125}I SAP in the Casein treated mice brain. Note less significant incorporation observed in control and BSA treated mice. (b), (c), and (d) shows correspondingly liver, spleen, and plasma of SAP. Most of the SAP accumulated in both control and Casein injected mice in various organs. However no significant in BSA incorporation in both control and Casein injected mice. Data show mean γ counting values (\pm SEM) from single, representative experiments. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$, related to control conditions.

increase may be at least partly attributed to the brain tissue expression of these proteins following inflammatory stimulus. The result of the present work suggests that peripheral inflammation significantly contributes to SAA and SAP transport across the brain and associated toxic responses.

Earlier studies indicate that circulating peptide and protein such as insulin and transthyrin and modified form of catalase gets transported either by adsorption or by facilitated through brain capillary endothelial cell wall [29-33]. Under normal condition SAA and SAP, which are the normal constituent of blood, which never cross the blood brain barrier (BBB). However during the inflammatory condition, SAA level increases considerably in the blood plasma, leading to the possibility of protofibrillar formation, which ultimately crosses the BBB. Such a relative interactive motif in the fibrillar proteins/peptides is already known in amyloid biochemistry.

Coraci et al reported that the class B scavenger receptor (CD 36) on microglial cells binds to fibrillar β -amyloid protein but not its non-fibrillar form [34]. Microglial cells get activated when their scavenger receptors bind to fibrillar amyloid. The cellular activation due to SAA fibrils are also implicated to RAGE receptors (Receptor for Advanced Glycation Endproducts) [35-37]. It was already estimated that RAGE binds SAA1 protein with nanomolar affinity. It was also shown that tissues with amyloid deposition increased expression of RAGE. Recently, apoSAA and mRNA expression has been demonstrated in the Syrian hamster brain following intra-peritoneal injection of the inflammatory stimulant, lipopolysaccharide, as well as patients with AD [38] indicating brain parenchymal cells expressed SAA mRNA in the inflammatory conditions. Since, at high concentration SAA, amyloid protofibrils formation is possible in the inflammatory condition, there is a possibility of SAA

SAA

SAP

Fig. 4. Fluorescence microscopic pictures representative in selective binding to (a) control for SAA and (c) control for SAP (b) SAA and (d) SAP in systemic amyloidosis brain endothelial cell capillaries viewed at a magnification $\times 40$

protofibrils crossing the BBB through RAGE that are expressed in the brain endothelial cell capillaries. Further, the binding of SAA protein to the RAGE receptors known to elicit the cellular oxidative response [39]. RAGE is found in most of the cells known to affect by amyloid namely hepatic, endothelial, neuronal, and microglial cells [40]. The consequences of SAA fibril-RAGE interaction include increased cellular oxidant, stress and microglial activation. Yan et al established by the triggering of inflammatory responses with fibrillar Prion protein [41]. They have shown that aged amyloid β fibrils, dramatically increased plasma IL-6 levels in mice. IL-6 is a multi-functional cytokine involved in the acute phase reactions and overproduction of SAA protein. Thus, these results suggest that systemic amyloidosis and central neurons inflammation responses could be interrelated.

Our results also indicate that along with SAA fibrils, SAP also crosses the BBB. The presence of SAP in peripheral and neuronal amyloid deposits is well documented [42]. However, the mRNA encoding SAP was not detected in the brain [43] indicating that cerebral SAP can be sourced from peripheral region. The present work is consistent with this hypothesis that the SAP, which is found in various inflammatory conditions in the brain, may be due to its crossing of BBB from the plasma.

Earlier reports [44] also have shown that the penetrated SAP can be toxic to the cortical neuron. The significant toxicity of SAA/SAP transportation to the brain raising the possibility that both these, either together or alone are involved in cerebral neurodegenerative disorders accompanied by amyloid deposition.

Fig.5: Fluorescence microscopic pictures representative in selective binding to (a) control for SAA and (c) control for SAP (b) SAA and (d) SAP in systemic amyloidosis brain sections viewing field at a magnification $\times 40$.

This suggests the possibility of involvement of SAA/amyloid fibril in neuronal damage. Suki et al [26] have shown SAA presence in the brain endothelial cell capillaries in stress conditions like high blood pressure in the brain and this can result in either local production of A-apo SAA in the brain endothelial cell capillaries or the inflammation lead to uptake of A-apo SAA from the plasma [32]. The result indicates SAA proteins influencing inflammatory condition can cross the BBB presumably due to receptor-mediated transport. It is likely that SAA may reach the brain endothelial cell capillaries as a result of their interaction with HDL because the HDL carries most of the SAA [45, 46].

4. CONCLUSION

The results of the experiment present the following conclusions. First, the SAA and SAP proteins are transported across the BBB in the mice with systemic amyloid disease. The

second conclusion is that the transported SAA along with SAP get localized in the brain.

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